

ISSUES OF PRODUCT PRICING IN THE ANALYSIS OF OPERATIONAL ACTIVITIES*Klichev Bakhtiyor Pardayevich*

Department of Finance and Accounting at Tashkent State University of Economics, e-mail: klichev.bakhtiyor@gmail.com,

ORCID: 0000-0001-6938-7897, Tel: +99890 8650088

Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Abstract The purpose of this article is to evaluate the newly developed products in business entities based on the technical and economic parameters of the product, the interests of consumers, their wishes, the market price of the reference product, and the conditions developed by the author. Integral methods, surveys, data grouping, and logical analysis methods were used in the calculations. When choosing a product, buyers choose more cost-effective products. Another feature of customer selection is that it compares the price of the product being purchased with the price of the best (reference) product on the market. The article provides analytical solutions for the calculation of the assessment based on these conditions. Comparing the technical and economic parameters of the product, the concept of pricing a new type of product is developed based on the indicators that customers pay the most attention to and the efficiency of use of the product is 5% higher than its price. In the calculations, only the technical and economic parameters of the product are obtained, and we will consider the analytical calculations on the remaining parameters in the formation of the assessment in our next articles.

Key words: price of product, parameters (options) of product, technical parameters (options), economical parameters (options), pricing policy, formulation models of price

ОПЕРАЦИОН ФАОЛИЯТ ТАҲЛИЛИДА МАҲСУЛОТГА БАҲО ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ*Кlichev Бахтиёр Пардаевич*

Тошкент Давлат Иқтисодий Университети

“Молия ва бухгалтерия ҳисоби” кафедраси

катта ўқитувчиси, e-mail: klichev.bakhtiyor@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-6938-7897, Tel: +99890 8650088

Аннотация Ушбу мақола мақсади ҳўжалик юритувчи субъектларда янги ишлаб чиқилган маҳсулотларга маҳсулотнинг техник ва иқтисодий параметрларидан келиб чиққан ҳолда, истеъмолчилар манфаатлари, истак-ҳўхишлари, бозордаги эталон маҳсулот баҳоси ҳамда муаллиф томонидан ишлаб чиқилган шартлар асосида баҳо шакллантириш ҳисобланади. Амалга оширилаётган ҳисоб-китобларда интеграл усул, сўровнома ўтказиш, маълумотларни гуруҳлаш, мантиқий таҳлил усулларида фойдаланилган. Харидорлар маҳсулот танлашда унинг ишлатиш самарадорлиги баҳосидан юқори турадиган маҳсулотларни таналашади. Харидор танловининг яна бир хўсўсияти харид қилинаётган маҳсулот баҳосини албатта, бозордаги энг яхши (эталон) маҳсулот баҳоси билан таққослайди. Мақолада мана шу шартлар асосида баҳо шакллантириш бўйича ҳисоб-китоблар амалга оширилиб таҳлилий ечимлар берилган. Маҳсулотнинг техник ва иқтисодий параметрлари таққосланиб, харидорлар энг кўп аҳамият берадиган кўрсаткичлар ҳамда маҳсулотнинг ишлатиш самарадорлиги унинг баҳосидан 5% юқори бўлиши шarti асосида янги турдаги маҳсулот нархини белгилаш концепцияси ишлаб чиқилган. Ҳисоблашларда маҳсулотнинг фақат техник ва иқтисодий параметрлари олинган бўлиб, баҳо шакллантиришда қолган параметрлар бўйича таҳлилий ҳисоб-китобларни кейинги тадқиқотларимизда кўриб чиқамиз.

Таянч сўзлар: маҳсулот баҳоси, маҳсулот параметрлари, техник параметрлар, иқтисодий параметрлар, баҳо сиёсати, баҳо шакллантириш моделлари

ВОПРОСЫ ЦЕНООБРАЗОВАНИЯ ПРОДУКЦИИ ПРИ АНАЛИЗЕ ОПЕРАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Кличев Бахтиёр Пардаевич

Старший преподаватель кафедры “Финансы и бухгалтерский учет” Ташкентского
Государственного Экономического Университета

e-mail: klichev.baxtiyor@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0001-6938-7897

Аннотация Цель данной статьи является разрабатывать цен продукции в хозяйствующих субъектах с учетом технических-экономических параметров продукции, интересов потребителей, их пожеланий, рыночной цены эталонной продукции и условий, разработанных автором. В расчетах использовались интегральные методы, опросы, группировка данных, методы логического анализа. Покупатели выбирают продукты, которые являются более экономически эффективными. Еще одна особенность потребительского отбора заключается в том, что он сравнивает цену приобретаемого товара с ценой лучшего (эталонного) товара на рынке. В статье приведены аналитические решения для расчета формирования оценки на основе этих условий. Сопоставляя технические-экономические параметры товара, разрабатывается концепция ценообразования нового вида товара исходя из показателей, на которые покупатели обращают наибольшее внимание и эффективность использования товара на 5% выше его цены. В расчетах получают только технические-экономические параметры изделия, а аналитические расчеты по остальным параметрам при формировании оценки мы рассмотрим в нашем следующем исследовании.

Ключевые слова: цена продукта, параметры (варианты) продукта, технические параметры (варианты), экономические параметры (варианты), ценовая политика, модели формулирования цены

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Introduction The efficiency of operational activities of business entities and the formation of positive financial results depend on the volume of production and sales. The increase in profit is inextricably linked to the cost of production and the price of the product.

As customers' willing to pay drives profit to the company, setting a good pricing policy will be significant for targeting profit, which requires keeping balance between customer's desire to pay at the good value and the company's cost covering and profit earnings (Nagle, & Müller, 2017)

Today, one of the main tasks of the analysis of operational activity is the formation of optimal prices for finished products (works, services) produced by economic entities. Today, when a very wide range of goods is offered, every buyer wants the efficiency of the purchased product to be higher than its price. Simply put, the buyer

wants the cheapest and highest quality product. To increase sales in today's market, where there is a wide range of products, works, and services, businesses need to make effective and comprehensive management decisions in pricing.

There are many studies on pricing policy and profitability in various countries. Van der Rest, et. al. (2018) analyzed the determination of room rate prices in the European hotel group which involve in complex activity system that required reorganizing into four spanning processes: developing, determining, learning, and negotiating prices. Borio et. al. (2017) investigated the relationship between the level of interest rates and the yield curve steepness against ROA. They discovered that this relationship is positive and enhances profitability. Modak, et. al., (2016) studied pricing policy and coordination for distribution channel with suggestion from

manufacturer and they revealed that in decentralized and centralized systems, the optimal pricing strategies can be proposed under two-part tariff and trading process.

There are many theories and models of price formation in product sales volume analysis, and manufacturers can apply the necessary methods in pricing based on industry characteristics, product range, market structure, and other indicators. We will focus on some of these models and theories.

- 1) **Model by Bertrand.**
- 2) **Model by Nash**
- 3) **Cost approach model.** Enterprise costs + corporate profits at a certain percentage = Price
- 4) **The model of value theory.** Enterprise costs + corporate profits at a certain percentage + customer interests and achievement = Price

In developed Western countries, one of the most important priorities in the field of marketing is to conduct research in the formation of prices, taking into account the interests of consumers. Among the economists who have conducted successful theoretical research in this area are Thomas R., Bernstein L.A. and Savitskaya G.V. such as scientists.

Optimal product pricing is also important in the analysis of employee financial incentives. (Klichev, 2022)

Owing to marketing globalization and increasing technological changes, the number of competitors and new sources of value for customers has increased which not necessarily led to rises in profit for the producers (Nagle, & Müller, 2017).

Methodology The research process used methods such as quantity and quality, cause and effect, statistical and economic analysis, data grouping, logical analysis, comparative analysis, sociological surveys.

Discussion Today, when consumer interests take precedence, there are several shortcomings in pricing based on the models mentioned in the introductory part of our article. In particular, Bertrand's two-way

game model, Nash's fair distribution model, and cost approach models are theoretical solutions, and failure to take into account the wishes, desires, and interests of buyers may lead to the price not being accepted by the buyer in the market..

Although the value theory of pricing assumes that the interests of the consumer should be taken into account, the lack of theoretical or practical suggestions on how to implement it is recognized as a shortcoming of this method.

Manufacturers and buyers have different attitudes towards product prices. If the price of the product is set by the manufacturer with a maximum limit that increases the profit, it is natural for the buyer to consider the price of the product as the minimum cost. In their work, R. Thomas and L.A. Bernstein argue that a price formed on the condition that a product has a certain efficiency relative to another product can be formed as a price in the market. However, neither these scientists nor the theories used in the formulation of the assessment presented in the introductory part of our article provide a model of assessment using exact calculations.

The buyer compares the price of each new product with the price of this type of reference product on the market. The first condition of the model we offer also depends on this factor: the price of the product we produce should never be higher than the price of the reference product. Otherwise, the buyer will definitely choose a product that has been consumed in advance and is considered a benchmark in the market. Once we ensure price uniformity, our assumption that the previously mentioned product should have a certain (higher than 1) efficiency relative to another product justifies itself (Klichev, 2014). That is, to attract a customer to a new product being manufactured or to convince a customer, our product must have an efficiency of at least 5% relative to the reference product.

It is advisable to approach the formation of product prices from the consumer's point of view (Klichev, Choriev,

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мавзусида халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман**

2021). According to the consumer, the purchased product must meet the following conditions:

$$\frac{\text{Product consumption efficiency}}{\text{Price of product}} > 1$$

or

Product consumption efficiency > Price of product

At first glance, this approach may be understandable to all, but it is a bit of a complicated process to express the efficiency of using a product in exact numbers to make accurate calculations.

According to the manufacturer, the efficiency of use of the product depends on its technical parameters. But in the opinion of the consumer, the efficiency of using the product should consist of the following components:

- one of the technical parameters of the purchased product should be a

priority (at the consumer's choice);

- the priority indicator should not be less than the same indicator of the reference (best on the market) product;
- the price of the product must be lower than the price of the reference product.

Summarizing the above points, the following conditions must be met for the price of the product to be formed as a price in the market:

- In formulating the price of a new product, of course, the price of the reference product should be taken as a basis;
- The efficiency of the product should be 5% higher than other similar products;
- The price of the product cannot be higher than the price of the reference product in the market provided 5% efficiency is available.

Table 1: Parameters of product

Parameters	Essence
Technical parameters	The composition of the product, the technical and technological level of its production and use, as well as the service life are considered.
Economic parameters	The price of the product, the level of service for the product, its volume and quality are considered
Ergonomic parameters	The suitability, convenience and usefulness of the use and consumption of the product for the human body will be considered
Aesthetic parameters	The appearance of the product, its suitability to the taste of the buyer, the degree of completeness of the product are considered
Normative parameters	The degree to which the product meets applicable international regulatory parameters and standards (ISO) will be considered

Based on the above conditions, we must consider the economic and technical parameters of the product in order to form an estimate using the proposed method. In general, the parameters of the product are many (Table 1), which parameter the buyer prefers depends on his socio-economic status. In countries with high living standards and incomes, the priority in the procurement process is given to the technical, ergonomic and aesthetic parameters of the product, while in countries with relatively low living standards and incomes, the priority is given to economic parameters.

Data Analysis and Findings In addition to increasing the company's profitability, an effective valuation policy has a positive impact on the growth of its business activity indicators, including quantitative and qualitative indicators of the company's operational efficiency. The importance of free evaluation and assessment of business activity of the organization in the context of high competition is of particular importance in the study of its financial condition, the formation of a strategic plan and development prospects. (Klichev, Tulaev 2021)

According to marketing research, 60-70% of consumers choose depending on the technical and economic parameters of the product. That is, the efficiency of using the product should be higher than the price of the

product. Therefore, in our proposed method, the technical and economic parameters are studied, and according to the degree of compliance of the product with these parameters, the ratio of new product to standard product, group and integral indicators are determined in the price formation process.

The ratio of a new product to a reference product (g) is determined by the ratio of the technical or economic functions of the product to the same function of the reference product:

$$g = \frac{F_0}{F_1} * 100$$

Here are:

g - the ratio of the new product to the reference product;

F_0 - parameters of new product;

F_1 - parameters of reference product.

The overall indicator (G) is the product of the ratio of the new product to the reference product (g) and the customer choice indicators (a).

$$G = g * a$$

Customer selection indicators (a) are the ratio of the total useful workload of a product (100% or 1 coefficient) distributed over parameter indicators. That is, the

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consumer determines which function of the product he is buying is the main one for him and gives a greater coefficient to this function, while the remaining functions are given a coefficient in the same way.

The method we propose is an integral indicator of the effectiveness of our new product relative to the reference product. The integral indicator (I) is determined by the ratio of the total group index of the product under study to the total group index of the reference product:

$$I = \frac{G_{tp}}{G_{ep}}$$

Here are:

G_{tp} - the sum of the total group indicators of technical parameters

G_{ep} - the sum of the total group indicators of economic parameters

If the integral value is suddenly higher, the product is considered competitive

and the product can find its place in the market (it should be in the ratio of 1.05 in the method we propose).

If the integral indicator is lower than one, it is necessary to carry out analytical work on economic parameters. Because in order to change the technical parameters, it is necessary to change the structure of production, technology, and this is a work that can not be done in the short term.

Let us consider the order of price formation on the basis of technical and economic parameters by a conditional example.

Conditional example. The company produces refrigerators “A”. Due to the fact that the product is new in the market, the task is to set the price, provided more efficient than the reference product “B”.

In order to form an estimate using the proposed method, we determine the parameters determined by the parameters of the new brand refrigerator “A” and the market reference brand refrigerator “B” (Table 2).

Table 2: Reports on product pricing

Indicators	new product “A” (F ₀)	reference product “B” (F ₁)	g	a	G
<i>Technical parameters</i>					
1. Full volume, dm ³	330	340	0,97	0,20	0,194
2. Common section, dm ³	190	200	0,95	0,22	0,235
3. Deep freeze, dm ³	80	80	1,0	0,2	0,2
4. Freezing power, kg / day	5,2	5	1,04	0,18	0,209
5. Term of use, years	12	10	1,2	0,12	0,106
6. Temperature of deep freeze, °C	-15	-16	0,94	0,08	0,0664
					G_{tp} = 1,01
<i>Economic parameters</i>					
1. Price, dollar (USA)	x	600	x/600	0,5	0,5*x/600
2. Warranty service period, months	40	36	1,11	0,25	0,278
3. Daily electricity consumption, kw	1,9	2,1	0,9	0,25	0,225
					G_{ep} = 0,278 + 0,225 + 0,5 * x/600

Based on the data in Table 2, our integral index is:

$$I = \frac{G_{tp}}{G_{ep}} = \frac{1,01}{0,278 + 0,225 + 0,5 * x / 600}$$

According to our proposed method, the new product must have a efficiency of 5% compared to the standard product. So, based on this condition, our above equation looks like this:

$$I = \frac{G_{tp}}{G_{ep}} = \frac{1,01}{0,278 + 0,225 + 0,5 * x / 600} = 1,05$$

From this equation we determine the unknown number (x). According to calculations, our unknown number is 550.8.

Conclusion

From the above calculations, it is clear that if we set a price of \$ 550.8 for our new product "A", we will fully meet the following conditions:

- The price of the reference product is taken as the basis for the formation of the price of a new product.
- 5% efficiency of our new product compared to the reference product;
- In addition to 5% efficiency, our new product is priced at \$ 49.2 less than the standard product price on the market.

In general, we can say that the price formed by this method, which we offer, will undoubtedly be accepted by the buyer in the market. Businesses may set a higher price cap in order to increase profits in the future. This requires the necessary analytical work on economic parameters (for example, by extending the warranty service life of a new product, it is possible to increase the price by a certain amount, while maintaining 5% efficiency over the reference product). Only in this case, economists should keep in mind that some of the economic parameters are inversely related.

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